

Angiogenic-Cytogenotoxic Biphasic Regulation of *Moringa oleifera* (Horseradish) Leaf Decoction to *Gallus gallus subsp. domesticus* (Red Junglefowl Chicken) Via Chorioallontoic Membrane Culture Technique

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The angiogenic-cytogenotoxic biphasic regulation of *Moringa oleifera* leaf decoction (MOLD) was ran into test trials via in-ovo chorioallontoic membrane (CAM) embryonic bioassay of *Gallus domesticus* culture. The study commenced by initially using three groups, two of which were the positive and negative controls, and one for the experimental group. After the induction of the three substances to the culture, there were significant results for both the angiogenic and cytogenotoxic manifestations of the exposed biocultures. After 5 days of the administration with the negative control (distilled water), the angiogenesis of the embryo went up to 30.9% compared to the initial untreated count. The corresponding cytogenotoxic activity was low at about 12.8% only. Meanwhile, the effect of the experimental group decreased the angiogenic count by 58.1%. Its linear effect was inversely evident with the cytotoxicity test, thereby having a sudden insurgence of 49.3% increase of aberrations. Lastly, the treatment with the positive control (Hydrogen peroxide), drastically decreased the angiogenic activity by 203.3% while effecting an upsurge of 69.2% during microscopy for cytogenotoxicity. Using ANOVA, there was a significant difference between the 3 groups on its effect to induce angiogenesis and cytogenotoxic activity. And according to Pearson's bivariate analysis, there was a negative biphasic regulation between the two variables. Thus, the negative correlation suggests a strong anti-angiogenic activity of the treatment relative to the increase in cytogenotoxic cases.

Keywords: *Moringa oleifera* leaf decoction (MOLD), In-ovo Chorioallontoic Membrane (CAM) embryonic bioassay, Distilled water, Hydrogen peroxide, Angiogenesis, Cytogenotoxicity.

Introduction

Currently, there is a rampant unprecedented increase in the usage of various medicinal herbs as one of the folk sources of human sustenance, therapeutically (Alimba *et. al.*, 2016).

One of these famous medicinal herbs is *Moringa oleifera* commonly known as malunggay. This plant is widely used by Filipinos in varied cuisines and have been constantly used as an important herbal remedy. On the other hand, international

English countries use the term Horseradish to name the shrub (Sandoval and Jimeno, 2013).

Horseradish belongs to the family *Moringaceae*. This plant usually grows as tall shrub and has sparse foliage and scanty leaves. This kind of deciduous plant can grow up to 8 meters tall. The leaf pattern is usually alternating and is tripinnate with an average growth length of 25-50 centimeters. There are 3-9 leaflets on each of the pinnules. These leaflets have small thin and ovate shape and are about 1-2 cm long (Ambi *et. al.*, 2011; Morton, 1991).

Prior to any kind of traditional infection-related treatment, this plant is usually prepared in solutions, aqueous extracts and decoctions and there have been research determining the mechanism of the innate chemicals which triggered the necessary effects (Sobita and Bhagirath, 2005).

In 2002, certain studies stated that despite the established approaches regarding medicinal herbs, there is a historic role that its capacity as a treatment, prevention and pharmacology cannot assume a hundred percent safeness due to its ununiformed and uncontrolled public usage (Bast *et al.*, 2002; Matthews *et al.*, 1999). That is why the studies relative to cytogenotoxicity help evaluate the effectiveness, equipped with safeness at the same time, of the folk health herbal products.

The succeeding reports depict an existence of relationship between the genotoxicity of a substance and carcinogenicity (Misra *et al.*, 2002). There is a theoretical efficacy that offset angiogenesis could lead to carcinoma, thus there is a direct establishmentarianism between angiogenic and cytogenotoxic properties of potent medicinal products (Nishida *et al.*, 2006).

There are series of studies regarding the genotoxic activities of *M. oleifera* leaf extracts and decoctions. Most of the experiments used plant bioassays. However, certain potential endotoxins and genotoxic substances could induce chromosomal damage only to animals, others could only affect plants. Basically, not all cases are one-way, other toxins could yield damages to both plant and animal cells. This triggered the group to conduct a research regarding the instilled effectivity of malunggay toxicity if it is still applicable to complex type of eukaryotic cells, those of the animals already (Wallace *et al.*, 2016).

During stable and unstable conditions happening inside the human body, angiogenesis constantly happen. This process continues to develop even in the progress of diseases or healthy recovery. Such cases of cancer and tumor proliferation emanates ideas that angiogenesis occur fast to be able to nourish the growing number of demanding cancer cells. On the brighter side, cases like post-surgery recovery, the body forms sudden capillary bifurcations. This

triggering moment helps the body supplement lost supply of oxygen and other necessary molecules (D'Onofrio, 2008; Adair and Montani, 2010).

Despite the body's condition to be ill or healthy, constant case of angiogenesis inside the human body is of but in a regular basis. Hemodynamics of capillaries are beneficial when the body is regulating regeneration from any damage and is harmful otherwise during multiple carcinoma occurrences (Adair and Montani, 2010).

It is within the general objective of the researchers to assess the cytogenotoxicity of the selected substance of interest in malunggay to embryonic cells already and whether it could have any relative association with angiogenic activities of the chicken during embryological development and create a notable data for further studies in carcinogenesis. As the team were notified that if there is a happenstance of new capillary growths coming from the existing blood vessels, either of veins or arteries, it is called angiogenesis. Angiogenesis is usually mediated with a complex multistage variation that causes neovascularization (Folkman, 1995; Klagsbrun and Moses, 1999).

Objectives

The general objective of the study is to determine the angiogenic-cytogenotoxic biphasic regulation of *Moringa oleifera* Leaf Decoction (MOLD) to *Gallus domesticus* embryonic bioassay via in-ovo Chorioallantoic Membrane (CAM) culture.

Specifically, this aims to:

1. Determine the angiogenic effect of MOLD to the chicken embryonic CAM bioassay on the following periodic counts:
 - a) Initial Count
 - b) Final Count
2. Examine the cytotoxic effect of MOLD to the chicken embryonic CAM bioassay through the following cytoplasmic aberration indices (CAI):
 - a) Microcytic erythrocytes
 - b) Macrocytic erythrocytes
 - c) Ghost cells
 - d) Dysmorphic erythrocytes

3. Analyze the genotoxic effect of MOLD to the chicken embryonic CAM bioassay through the following nuclear chromosomal aberration indices (NCAI):
 - a) Binucleated erythrocytes
 - b) Fragmented erythrocytes
 - c) Sticky tetraploids
 - d) Heterokaryonic C-mitosis
 - e) Dikaryonic C-mitosis
4. Evaluate the gross cytogenotoxic regulation of MOLD to the chicken embryonic CAM bioassay by these conjunctive aberration indices:
 - a) Cytoplasmic Aberration Index (CAI)
 - b) Nuclear Chromosomal Aberration Index (NCAI)
5. Probe if there is a correlative angiogenic-cytogenotoxic biphasic regulation of MOLD to the chicken embryonic CAM bioassay utilizing the following substances:
 - a) Distilled water (negative control)
 - b) MOLD (treatment)
 - c) Hydrogen peroxide (positive control)

Research Design

The study probed the propositional objectives by utilizing quasi-experimental research design (Calmorin and Calmorin, 2005). This experimental model enables the group to gather data by testing the ability of the treatment to induce angiogenesis and cytogenotoxicity running in parallel with the effects of distilled water (negative) and Hydrogen peroxide (positive). After which, a descriptive correlational bivariate analysis was used at the end to compare the two concretized mean data gathered from angiogenesis and cytogenotoxicity tests. This study is pivoted on the grounds of an experimental research, having to utilize controls, to test if there is a significant difference on the angiogenic and cytogenotoxic effect the MOLD treatment could induce. To avoid perplexing results, the group counted the initial growths of blood vessels with its sum subtracted to the total growth after 24 hours on the 5th day of treating. The framework of the utilized experimental methodology was derived from the protocol of (Yildiz et al., 2013) with partial modifications to suffice the

necessary results. The software Microsoft excel was utilized as an auto-analyzer to interpret mean data.

Research Sampling

A total of eighteen (18) sample treatment sites were distributed among the six (6) embryonic cultures using sterile filter discs. The bioassay setups ran with three (3) treatment sites per embryonic culture. There were three groups that were tested in parallel, and these were the cultures treated with; Distilled water, MOLD and Hydrogen peroxide. Each of the group had two (2) replicates to ensure well-averaged results. The angiogenic scoring was assessed utilizing 1-inched perimeter grid enclosure on each of the filter discs. Blood sample were collected for cytogenotoxicity readings. Two (2) blood smears were derived in each of the culture having four (4) slides averaged in each of the test and control groups.

Table 1.0 The angiogenesis sampling depicting the culture-treatment association relative to the number of sample sites of which the filter discs were put. Each replicate has 3 sample sites.

ANGIOGENESIS SAMPLING					
Variable	Substance	Replicate Culture	Sample Sites		
Negative	Distilled water	A	1	2	3
		B	1	2	3
Treatment	MOLD	A	1	2	3
		B	1	2	3
Positive	Hydrogen peroxide	A	1	2	3
		B	1	2	3

Table 1.1 The cytogenotoxicity sampling depicting the culture-treatment association relative to the number of blood smear samples. Each replicate has 2 blood smear samples for reading.

CYTOGENOTOXICITY SAMPLING				
Variable	Substance	Replicate Culture	Blood Smears	
Negative	Distilled water	A	1	2
		B	1	2
Treatment	MOLD	A	1	2
		B	1	2
Positive	Hydrogen peroxide	A	1	2
		B	1	2

Materials and Methods

A. Pre-testing phase

1. Preparation of Materials

Dispensable

The group borrowed the following materials from the institution laboratory to be utilized for the pre-testing, testing and post-testing activities. The glassware borrowed were Petri dishes, beakers, graduated cylinders, test tubes and vials. The group also borrowed alcohol lamp for *in promptu* heat sterilization. Pipet tips were borrowed for treatment administration. Forceps, funnel, and water bath were also borrowed from the lab.

Procurable

Unavailable materials in the laboratory were acquired by the group such as egg cracker, humidity gauge, surgical blade and colored disk markers. The group purchased orcein powder, Wright's stain, buffer, filter paper, 0.22 um Millipore filter, tuberculin syringe, capillets, cotton balls, aluminum foil, plastic cups, distilled water, and Hydrogen peroxide solution.

Equipment

Automated and manual equipment in the laboratory like autoclave, biosafety hood, incubator, refrigerator, micropipette, coulter counter, computerized aided microscope and dry heat oven were used all throughout the study.

2. Sterilization Techniques

Materials

Equipment like Forceps, Filter Disks, Surgical Blade, Pipet tips, Petri dishes were autoclaved at 120 degrees Celsius under moist heat and 15 psi for 30 minutes. .

Solutions

Distilled water and Hydrogen peroxide were kept sterile all throughout. MOLD stock solution was pre-warmed, centrifuged and was filtered using 0.22 micrometer Millipore filter to avoid contamination with bacterial and fungal spores as well as bacterial cells.

3. Pre-treatment In-ovo Culture

Egg Handling and Transport

Proper handling and management of equipment and materials to be used in the study will be based on the protocols stated in Hatchery Management Guide and Incubating and hatching eggs (COBB, 2013; Cartwright and Archer, 2013).

Personnel assigned with handling of eggs should have his hand sanitized. Movement of eggs should be kept at minimum. Eggs should be turned twice daily when stored over a week Eggs should be always handled with care. During transportation, eggs must be kept between 20-23 degrees Celsius.

Egg Collection

Fertilized eggs of Red Junglefowl hens (*Gallus domesticus*) are the group's preference for choosing the test subjects. A standard set by the researchers (COBB, 2013) in determining the eggs that would be collected. Only the eggs that were fresh and fertile were be used in this study and eggs that were soiled, cracked, rounded, blood stained, dirty, and unusually small or large were automatically disregarded. Collected eggs were labelled with assigned code ready for transfer in the sterile tray for incubation.

Egg Storage

Storage of eggs was done in accordance with the protocol described (Cartwright and Archer, 2013). In the laboratory, eggs were stored in an incubator with automatic agitator with a temperature between 98 to 102 ° F (36.6 to 38.8 ° C) with a relative humidity of 70-80%. The eggs were rotated from side to side twice daily, over a 90-degree angle scale.

4. Candling Viability Test

Candling was done to determine the egg viability for growth and good for CAM culture. This technique was done every 24 hrs at 6 pm for 5 days prior to creation of partial opening for treatment induction. The group utilized a strong flashlight and identified for the presence of the air sac, nucleus, heart and proliferating blood vessels.

5. Hammock Preparation

Hammocks or culture chambers were used as cotton bed cushion for the eggs of the embryo allowing the researchers to have a better viewing of the developing embryo especially the formation of blood vessels. Culture chambers were prepared by using plastic cups. Two small holes were made on the opposite sides of the cup to allow gas exchange for the embryo while a petri dish was utilized as a sterile transparent protective cover.

6. Treatment Preparation

Selection of Horseradish Tree

Prior to collection and preparatory processes, plant identification and verification was done first to ensure that only the right plant species was used during

decoction. The mobile app – *PlantSnap* was used to confirm the plant located in housing village close to our school.

Collection and Preparation of Horseradish Leaves

Initially, the leaves were collected from a bushy *M. oleifera* tree during the month of August utilizing the method used by Shukla and Tripathi (2015) with little modifications. The leaves sample were then collected at exactly 6 o'clock in the morning the leaves were washed with tap water to remove any surface impurities. The mechanism behind the collection time was indicated in the Asian Journal of Plant Sciences (Teshome *et. al.*, 2013). It was essential to prevent drying temperature in harvesting the leaves to avoid erroneous biochemical content decocted. Only the dark green mature leaflets were chosen for the succeeding procedures. The fresh sample was labelled, kept in an air-tight plastic container until transported to the Research Laboratory.

Treatment Decoction

The leaves were set to undergo boiling, solutionization, filtration, and infusion processes. The researchers utilized the method used by Ewansiha *et al.*, (2014) with some modifications from Martins *et al.*, (2015) to suffice the research objectives. Weigh 500 grams of horseradish leaves. Measure 500 milliliter of distilled water. Prepare 1000 mL beaker and preheat it in a water bath. Slowly add the leaves to the boiling solution. Infuse water constantly in the extract to maintain the volume. Note that only the water evaporates and not the pure decoction. Always observe to remove over boiled leaves prior to adding some. The decoction is complete once all the leaves were utilized. Let the decoction cool down and transfer in Erlenmeyer flask. Cover with a stopper then store in the refrigerator under – 4 degrees.

7. Control Preparation

Negative Control

The group purchased Wilkin's distilled that is commercially available.

Positive Control

The group utilized a commercially available 3% Hydrogen peroxide to be the positive control for angiogenesis and cytogenotoxicity (Jeronimo *et al.*, 2017; Ruizo *et al.*, 2017).

8. In-ovo CAM Bioassay Culture

The study utilized a modified method described by Yalcin *et. al.*(2010) and Fisher (1993). This specific *in vitro* culture encompassed on the

preparation of the culture chamber, as well as the transformation of the *in ovo* culture into a directly observable CAM bioassay.

9. Markers and Labels

The group devised a way to remember the treatment sites and filter discs including the location of the proliferating new blood vessels, primary, secondary and tertiary blood vessels. They used coloured discs to indicate the direction around the cover Petri dish.

B. Testing phase

1. Substance induction and distribution

The treatment and control administration were done by pipetting 5 microliters of substance in each of the filter paper discs using 1 microliter-calibrated micropipette. Discs and substances were replaced and renewed every after 24hrs during 7pm.

2. Monitoring

The growth of the blood vessels was at least monitored as well as the survivability of the chick embryo during the treatment phase for 5 consecutive days. Note that the angiogenic and cytogenotoxic scoring was not done by rate per day and was examined after the 5th day, pre and post specimen collection.

C. Post-Testing phase

1. Angiogenesis Test

Macrographic Imaging

The group utilized the CPH1821 model of 8.1.0 – M_V3_P10 android camera to take graphic samples for angiogenic counting.

Angiogenic Scoring

The scoring was done individually with each of the treatment site counting frame. The grid size was 1.5 x 1.5 cm area of counting. The 3 treatment sites were summed up and were averaged. The 2 averaged culture count per treatment group were averaged again to get the final averaged group score.

2. Cytogenotoxicity Test

Specimen Collection

A 1cc tuberculin syringe (2mL) was utilized to collect blood from primary blood vessels. With areas hard to collect blood due to small blood vessels, the group puncture them first and utilized an anticoagulated capillet.

Blood Smearing

The group preferred using short-sized thin smear for easy reading and to adapt the availability of few samples collected. They utilized 25 x 75 x 1 mm frosted glass slide.

Staining

The group utilized two types of stain. For reading purposes, buffered Wright's stain was utilized, determining the total counts, types of aberration and normally dividing mitotic embryonic nrbc. Wright's stain and buffered was immediately filtered from the stock solution to avoid too much powder clumping under the microscope during reading. The group also utilized isotonic orcein to visually confirm the dominance of chromosomes inside the mitotic cells. The stain was prepared by modifying the aceto-orcein manufacturer's manual. Instead of adding 90 mL glacial acetic acid, 90 mL NSS and 1g of orcein powder were mixed. As it was pretested, aceto-orcein indeed lysed the nrbc cytoplasm when glacial acetic acid was used as diluent.

Microscopy

A computer aided microscope under 1250x magnification was used to visualize the cytoplasmic and nuclear structure of the erythrocytes. Mitotic Phase Indices (MPI) were as follows: Prophase, Metaphase, Anaphase and Telophase. Under the MPIs, cytoplasmic aberrations under prophase (CAI) are: Macrocytic nucleated rbc, Microcytic nucleated rbc, Dysmorphic nrbc and Ghost cell. While the nuclear aberrations (NCAI) were: Metaphase – heterokaryon and dikaryon C-mitosis, Anaphase – sticky tetraploid/bridging, Telophase – binucleated erythrocytes and fragmented erythrocytes. Every smear was evaluated by counting 500 red blood cells and from these, the different indices were noted. The initial reading were done by the group members and

the quality control was done by the group leader to ensure consistent reading.

Micrographic Imaging

The computer aided microscope was capable of clear vision and real time computer imaging. The CPH1821 android camera was also used for backup pictures.

Results and Discussions

The *Gallus domesticus* embryonic bioassay was used to determine if the *M. oleifera* Leaf Decoction was able to produce considerable significant angiogenesis activity. Macrographic samples attached on Appendix III shows a full extension of the comparison on the culture in the pre-treatment stage versus its new angiogenic score upon post-treatment phase.

Figure 1.1 Angiogenic effect of MOLD on the chicken embryonic culture.

Note: Macrograph (a) shows the pre-treatment initial growth of the treatment group A. The image on the right (b) depicts the anti-angiogenic effect of MOLD after exposure to post-treatment.

On the tabular data entailing below, it shows the statistically untreated results, already able to show the preliminary differences of the data gathered.

Table1.2 Angiogenic Effect of MOLD to *Gallus domesticus* Embryonic Bioassay

Angiogenesis									
Replicate	Distilled water			MOLD			Hydrogen peroxide		
	Initial	Final	%	Initial	Final	%	Initial	Final	%
1	50.3	70.31	39.8%	65.7	36.7	-55.9%	23	10.7	-215.6%
2	98.7	120.3	21.9%	32.7	19.7	-60.2%	6.3	3.3	-190.9%
			30.9%			-58.1%			-203.3%

The raw data above shows that the negative control, distilled water, induced angiogenic activity with a mean value of 30.9% increased percentile count after the substance administration. The treatment group showed anti-angiogenic response with a decrease of 58.1% angiogenic count compared to its untreated results. On the other hand, results from the positive control, Hydrogen peroxide, depicted a highly

distinctive anti-angiogenic result with an absolute decrease of 203.3% from the initial count.

The bar graph below concretely shows the percentage of decrease or increase before and after the treatment phase. Both positive control and treatment group exhibited anti-angiogenic activity with the negative group still showing progressive angiogenesis.

Table 1.3 The ANOVA treatment for the angiogenic scoring of all 3 variable groups.

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	55859.37333	2	27929.68667	176.5858	0.000773	9.552094
Within Groups	474.495	3	158.165			
Total	56333.86833	5				

Upon application of the one-way ANOVA, it was found out that the **F tabular value**, equal to **176.59**, was higher than the **F critical value**, which was **9.55**. The study had rejected the first null hypothesis therefore there was a significant difference among the angiogenic scores induced by the 3 substances.

Aside from the macroscopic angiogenic scoring, a computer aided microscopy was performed to test if there is any cytoplasmic and nuclear abnormalities the substances could induce. After series of blood smear readings, examination showed micrographs of abnormal mitotic erythrocyte.

Figure 1.3 Microscopic examination of chicken embryo blood smear for cytotoxicity.

Micrograph (A) shows an erythrocyte undergoing macrocytosis. **Micrograph (B)** shows the topmost erythrocyte undergoing microcytosis. **Micrographs (C, D, E)** shows cases of erythrocytes resorting into ghost cell morphism. **Micrograph (F, G, H)** are some

dysmorphic and pyknotic poikilocytes. All of the images showed were cytotoxic abnormalities derived from cytoplasmic origin inside the nucleated erythrocytes of chicken embryo.

Table 1.4 Cytotoxic Effect of MOLD to *Gallus domesticus* Embryonic Bioassay

Cytotoxicity						
Replicate	Distilled water		MOLD		Hydrogen peroxide	
	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
1	116	11.6%	452	45.2%	564	53.8%
2	102	10.2%	487	48.7%	544	54.4%
		10.9%		46.95%		54.1%

The raw data above shows that the negative control, distilled water, induced cytotoxic activity with a mean value of 10.9% on the embryonic culture. The treatment group showed high case of about 46.95% mean cytotoxicity. On the other hand, results from the positive control, Hydrogen peroxide, depicted a highly distinctive cytotoxicity result with a mean value of 54.1%.

Table 1.5 The ANOVA treatment for the cytotoxicity scoring of all 3 variable groups.

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	2144.643333	2	1072.321667	441.5875	0.000197	9.552094
Within Groups	7.285	3	2.428333333			
Total	2151.928333	5				

Upon application of the one-way ANOVA, it was found out that the **F tabular value**, equal to **441.59**, is higher than the **F critical value**, which is **9.55**. The study had rejected the first null hypothesis. There is a significant difference among the cytotoxic cases induced by the 3 substances.

Another computer aided microscopy was performed to test if there are nuclear abnormalities the substances could induce. After series of blood smear readings, examination showed micrographs of abnormal mitotic erythrocytes exhibiting genotoxic activities.

Figure 1.4 Microscopic examination of chicken embryo blood smear for genotoxicity.

Note: **Micrographs (A, B)** shows a late and early binucleated erythrocytes. This happens when the two nucleus are present yet the nucleated erythrocyte forgoes further division thus forfeiting telophase. **Micrograph C** is a case of sticky tetraploid or bridging chromosome. **Micrographs (D, E)** depicts

fragmented cases of erythrocytes of which nuclear content shows chromosomal scattering. **Micrographs (F, G)** are cases of heterokaryonic erythrocytes while **Micrograph H** is a case of dikaryonic erythrocytes, both of which are cases of C-mitosis.

Table 1.6 Genotoxic Effect of MOLD to *Gallus domesticus* Embryonic Bioassay

Genotoxicity						
Replicate	Distilled water		MOLD		Hydrogen peroxide	
	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
1	21	2.1%	30	3.0%	154	11.6%
2	17	1.4%	17	1.7%	141	14.1%
		1.7%		2.35%		12.8%

The raw data above shows that the negative control, distilled water, induced genotoxicity activity with a mean value of 1.7% on the embryonic culture. The treatment group showed high case of about 2.35% mean genotoxicity. On the other hand, results from the positive control, Hydrogen peroxide, depicted a highly distinctive genotoxicity result with a mean value of 12.8%.

Table 1.7 The ANOVA treatment for the genotoxicity scoring of all 3 variable groups.

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	155.88	2	77.94	55.47331	0.004272	9.552094
Within Groups	4.215	3	1.405			
Total	160.095	5				

Upon application of the one-way ANOVA, it was found out that the **F tabular value**, equal to **55.47**, is higher than the **F critical value**, which is **9.55**. The study had rejected the first null hypothesis. There is a significant difference among the genotoxic cases induced by the 3 substances.

Prior to correlating results of microscopic examination to macroscopic test, cytotoxic and genotoxic results were combined in a summative manner.

Table 1.8 Cytogenotoxic Effect of MOLD to *Gallus domesticus* Embryonic Bioassay

Cytogenotoxicity									
Replicate	Distilled water			MOLD			Hydrogen peroxide		
	Cyto	Geno	Total	Cyto	Geno	Total	Cyto	Geno	Total
1	11.6%	2.1%	13.7%	45.2%	3.0%	48.2%	53.8%	11.6%	68.8%
2	10.2%	1.4%	11.9%	48.7%	1.7%	50.4%	54.4%	14.1%	69.6%
	12.8%			49.3%			69.2%		

The raw data above shows that the negative control, distilled water, induced cytogenotoxicity activity with a mean value of 12.8% on the embryonic culture. The treatment group showed high case of about 49.3% mean cytogenotoxicity. On the other hand, results from the positive control, Hydrogen

peroxide, depicted a highly distinctive cytogenotoxicity result with a mean value of 69.2%.

And lastly, this quasi-experimental study used a descriptive bivariate correlational analysis having to utilize Pearson’s formula to know if there is a correlation between the two variables

Table 1.9 Angiogenic and Cytogenotoxic Effect of MOLD to the biocultures.

Biphasic Regulation		
Substance	Angiogenesis	Cytogenotoxicity
Distilled water	30.9%	12.8%
MOLD	-58.1%	49.3%
Hydrogen peroxide	-203.3%	69.2%

On the raw data showed above, upon an increase in the cytogenotoxic activity within the in-ovo culture, the angiogenesis activity decreases. There is an indirect relationship between the two in general, prior to statistical treatment.

Table 2.0 Pearson’s correlation for angiogenic-cytogenotoxic biphasic regulation.

	Column 1	Column 2
Column 1	1	
Column 2	-0.954319661	1

As the data were reflected above, there is a negative correlation between the angiogenic activity and cytogenotoxicity of the treatments could induce in the embryonic bioassays. It suggests that an increase in cytogenotoxicity promotes decrease in angiogenesis, thus this negative correlation depicting an anti-angiogenic effect relative to a direct cytogenotoxic activity.

Conclusions

1. Upon the determination of the angiogenic effect of MOLD to the chicken embryonic CAM bioassay on the following periodic counts; Initial Count, Final Count, the study was able to found that the negative control had consistent progressive angiogenesis with a tabulated data from culture A, 151 to 211 blood vessels count after 5 days of treatment, having a 39.8% increase. While on culture B, the

untreated count was 296 and became 361 via post-treatment having 21.9% increase. The average angiogenic activity for the negative control, distilled water, is an increase of 30.9%. For the *Moringa oleifera* Leaf Decoction treated group, culture A had an initial count of 197 then became less of about 110 after day 5. The culture showed a 55.9% decrease in count. For culture B, it was from 90 down to 59 counts, having a total of 60.2% decrease in angiogenic count. The average angiogenic activity for the treatment group is a decrease of 58.1%. Then upon exposure to the positive control, Hydrogen peroxide, the initial count of culture A was 69 going down to 32, thus having a decrease of 215.6%. On the other side, culture B went down from 19 to 10 having a rough percentage decrease of about 190.9% creating an average of 203.3% total percentile decrease.

2. During the examination of the cytotoxic effects of MOLD to the chicken embryonic CAM bioassay by these following cytoplasmic aberration indices (CAI); Microcytic erythrocytes, Macrocytic erythrocytes, Ghost cells, Dymorphic erythrocytes, the study found out that that the negative control, distilled water, induced cytotoxic activity with a mean value of 10.9% on the embryonic culture. The treatment group showed high case of about 47.0% mean cytotoxicity. On the other hand, results from the positive control, Hydrogen peroxide, depicted a highly distinctive cytotoxicity result with a mean value of 54.1%.

3. Then after analysing the genotoxic effects of MOLD to the chicken embryonic CAM bioassay through these following nuclear chromosomal aberration indices (NCAI); Binucleated erythrocytes, Fragmented erythrocytes, Sticky tetraploids, Heterokaryonic C-mitosis, Dikaryonic C-mitosis, the data reflected of which the negative control, distilled water, induced genotoxicity activity with a mean value of 11.7% on the embryonic culture. The treatment group showed high case of about 2.35% mean genotoxicity. On the other hand, results from the positive control, Hydrogen peroxide, depicted a highly distinctive genotoxicity result with a mean value of 12.8%.

4. As the researchers were evaluating the gross cytogenotoxic regulation of MOLD to the chicken embryonic CAM bioassay by these conjunctive aberration indices; Cytoplasmic

Aberration Index (CAI), Nuclear Chromosomal Aberration Index (NCAI), the study depicted that the negative control, distilled water, induced cytogenotoxicity activity with a mean value of 12.8% on the embryonic culture. The treatment group showed high case of about 49.3% mean cytogenotoxicity. On the other hand, results from the positive control, Hydrogen peroxide, depicted a highly distinctive cytogenotoxicity result with a mean value of 49.4%.

5. Finally, the probation of which if there is a correlative angiogenic-cytogenotoxic biphasic regulation of MOLD to the chicken embryonic CAM bioassay utilizing the following substances; Distilled water (negative control), MOLD (treatment), Hydrogen peroxide (positive control), simply showed that there is a negative correlation between the angiogenic activity and cytogenotoxicity of the treatments could induce in the embryonic bioassays. It suggests that an increase in cytotoxicity promotes decrease in angiogenesis, thus this negative - **0.954319661** correlation depicting an anti-angiogenic effect relative to a direct cytogenotoxic activity.

Therefore, there is really an angiogenic and cytogenotoxic biphasic regulation the *Moringa oleifera* Leaf Decoction (MOLD) could induce in the *Gallus domesticus* embryonic bioassay.

Recommendations

The group highly recommends the following extensive propositions for the advancement and further development of this new research ground on the requisition against carcinogenesis.

1. Find out other cytotoxic and genotoxic abnormalities using other sampling techniques.
2. Utilize the embryonic bioassay ex-ovo culture for wider area of filter discs occupancy.
3. Determine the active biochemical component through phytochemical analysis in DOST.
4. Determine under gene analysis the cytogenetic cause of the abnormalities.
5. Use other methods for the treatment like ethanolic extraction or soxhlation.
6. Utilize other significant herbal sources for the decoction treatment.
7. Employ May-Grunwald stain and Isotonic Orcein for comparative analysis.
8. Shift to the usage of mammalian in-vivo cultures like albino mice and zebrafishes.

9. Evaluate the hematological indices of the samples collected.
10. Increase the length of time exposure of the treatment towards the biocultures.

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